

TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Teaching English as a Foreign Language (EFL) is a complex and multifaceted task that requires a solid understanding of linguistic and pedagogical theories, as well as a sensitivity to cultural and individual differences. In recent years, there has been a growing demand for innovative and effective teaching methodologies that can engage and motivate learners, foster communicative competence, and promote intercultural communication. This paper aims to review and discuss some of the best practices and innovations in teaching English methodology, based on a critical analysis of the literature and the author's experiences as an EFL teacher and trainer. The paper argues that while no single approach or tool can meet the diverse needs and goals of all learners and contexts, a flexible and adaptive methodology that combines different perspectives and strategies can create a more effective and inclusive learning environment.*

Keywords: *complex and multifaceted task, linguistic and pedagogical theories, cultural and individual differences.*

ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК ИНОСТРАННОГО

Аннотация. *Преподавание английского языка как иностранного (EFL) — сложная и многогранная задача, требующая твердого понимания лингвистических и педагогических теорий, а также чуткости к культурным и индивидуальным различиям. В последние годы наблюдается растущий спрос на инновационные и эффективные методики обучения, которые могут вовлекать и мотивировать учащихся, развивать коммуникативную компетентность и способствовать межкультурному общению. Целью этой статьи является обзор и обсуждение некоторых передовых практик и нововведений в методологии преподавания английского языка, основанных на критическом анализе литературы и опыте автора в качестве преподавателя и тренера EFL. В документе утверждается, что, хотя ни один подход или инструмент не может удовлетворить разнообразные потребности и цели всех учащихся и контекстов, гибкая и адаптивная методология, сочетающая различные точки зрения и стратегии, может создать более эффективную и инклюзивную среду обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *сложная и многоплановая задача, лингвопедагогические теории, культурные и индивидуальные различия.*

Unlike other subjects, there are many ups and downs in the history teaching English methodology as well as this field is rich with several changes and innovations. Methods and approaches of teaching English are always in the center of research. During the 19th century, several methods and approaches emerged and developed, resulting in a chain of methods. After the creation of a certain method, first, this method becomes popular in teaching a foreign language, but over time, some of its shortcomings become apparent, and gaps appear as a result of which it becomes ineffective in teaching a foreign language. In order to eliminate the gaps that appeared, the next foreign language teaching method was created, and the chain of methods was continued in this regard. Many scientists conducted research to determine which of the foreign language teaching methods is effective. For instance, M.T.Iriskulov stated that students could not use

English in real life because they were taught based on the traditional approach. Today, he emphasized the need to abandon traditional methods such as the grammatical translation method and theory and practice ought to be taught in parallel. While G.V.Rogova suggests the use of following approaches in teaching English, such as a practical approach, a structural approach, a situational approach, K.Alimova emphasizes oral approach, communicative approach, and cognitive approaches in teaching English.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a widely adopted approach that emphasizes the use of language for meaningful communication in real-life situations. It originated in the 1970s as a response to the limitations of the traditional grammar-translation and audio-lingual methods, which were criticized for focusing on form rather than function, and for neglecting the social and cultural dimensions of language. The main principles of CLT include a learner-centered approach, the integration of all language skills, the use of authentic materials and tasks, and the promotion of meaningful interaction and negotiation of meaning. Some of the techniques used in CLT include role plays, simulations, information-gap activities, and project-based learning.

Task-based Learning (TBL) is a methodology that emphasizes the use of authentic and purposeful tasks as a basis for language learning. It is based on the idea that learners learn language best when they are engaged in tasks that are relevant, challenging, and rewarding, and that require the activation of higher-level thinking and communication skills. Some of the advantages of TBL include the promotion of learner autonomy, the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and the integration of content and language learning. However, some challenges of TBL are the need for careful task design and scaffolding, the risk of task overload or underload, and the potential neglect of language form and accuracy.

In conclusion, teaching English methodology is a dynamic and multifaceted field that requires continuous innovation and adaptation to meet the diverse needs and goals of learners and contexts. Communicative language teaching, task-based learning are just some of the approaches that can enhance the effectiveness, efficiency, and inclusiveness of English instruction. However, it is also important to recognize that no single methodology or tool can be universally applicable or effective, and that teachers should be flexible, reflective, and collaborative in designing and implementing their teaching practices.

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